

How to Improve English?

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Abstract: This study aimed to investigate how English learning applications develop English skills, listening, speaking, reading, and writing of undergraduate students, majoring in English. In order to find out the result, the online interview is used in this study. The interviewees were 5 undergraduates' students, who major in English. The finding revealed that the participants enhanced and developed their English skills by using English learning applications. Additionally, the participants are motivated to study English through the English learning applications.

Keywords: Laura Kabelka conversations practice Learning, English, Listening, Speaking, Film, Activities, Improve, Develop aural and oral skills

People in a variety of countries use English to communicate. An increased level of English proficiency can be helpful when seeking employment, pursuing higher education, or adapting to a multicultural society. Understanding English can allow you to communicate with more people and improve your job prospects. In this article, we explore ways to improve your English skills, examine why improving your English skills is important, and review various tips to help you improve your skills. Discovering ways to improve your English skills begins with the four basic language skills of speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Receptive input, including listening and reading, exposes people to authentic language. Speaking and writing are examples of productive output, which is the action of producing language as part of the learning process. The following is a list of ways to improve your English skills

There are 5 ways to quickly improve your English language skills:

By Laura Kabelka

If English isn't your first language, you might find you need to take an English language proficiency exam such as the IELTS or the TOEFL as part of your application to study abroad. These tests may seem straightforward, but learning to write and speak in a sophisticated and eloquent manner in a new language doesn't come easily. In order to succeed, you'll need to put a lot of continuous effort into learning a new language, but there are some quick fixes that can help to boost your test performance at short notice.

If the exam is just a few weeks away, here are some ways to quickly improve your English language skills.

Watch movies in English

Watching series on Netflix might not exactly improve your debating skills or formal register, but it helps you to understand the language better, get used to colloquial, conversational forms of English and implicitly get a feeling for the language. Also, you could try to pick out words that sound highly informal and look up their more scholarly counterparts. Of course, there is also a plethora of documentaries (try anything by David Attenborough to start you off) to be found online as well. Being exposed to a language for the length of a movie might help you to actually start thinking in English.

Immerse yourself in English language news

Try to sample a broad range of English language newspapers, including broadsheets as well as magazines and tabloids. As well as helping you keep up to date with current affairs, this range of news sources will also expand your vocabulary. Another advantage is that you will also become more comfortable with how words are spelt and the contexts in which they are used.

Start a vocabulary book of useful words.

Either in a notebook or on your computer, start making a list of useful words and phrases. Every time you hear or see a word you're not familiar with, note it down. Don't only focus on the word itself, but search for synonyms and phrases in which it's used. After all, you might understand what words such as "precedence" or "tantalizing" mean, but do you know how to use them accurately?

Have conversations in English

As helpful as listening and reading tasks may be, you also need to use English interactively and practice your own speaking skills. If you're lucky, you'll be friends with a few native speakers who can help you out, but if not then try to meet up with someone else studying English. Another option is to talk to yourself in the mirror or record yourself. Listening to the sound of your own voice might be a little bit awkward at first, but you will be able to hear mistakes of which you weren't previously aware.

Practice, practice, practice

Let's face it, academic phrases won't just fall from heaven and straight into your brain. Even if your English is already quite good, don't be complacent and underestimate stressful factors such as the time pressure in an exam. You still have to practice, no matter how much time you have left before your big day. Try coming

up with a word of the day, and then try to employ it as often as possible. If you do this, don't waste time on extremely specific words you will never actually use. Instead, focus on conversational English which is likely to be relevant in the exam.

Practice Makes Perfect: English Conversation

For those preparing for their IELTS speaking test, this is the ultimate resource for you.

This book breaks down complex concepts of grammar, syntax, pronunciation, and word usage into simpler frameworks, making it much easier for non-native English speakers to understand.

With clear and helpful instructions as well as tailored exercises for each section, readers are highly encouraged to put what they learned into practice by forming personalized conversations.

With consistent practice and hard work, you'll be one step closer to gaining a more confident style of speaking and passing your IELTS speaking test!

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